

distribution. Our interest to elucidate the mechanism of the oxidation of organic compounds by Ce^{IV} in presence of micelles prompted us to study the kinetics of oxidation in presence of cationic micelles. This communication incorporates the results of a kinetic study of oxidation of acetophenone by Ce^{IV} in presence of *N*-dodecylpyridinium chloride (NDPC).

Experimental

All the chemicals are of A.R. grade. Acetophenones and substituted acetophenones were purified. Solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The surfactant NDPC was recrystallised from ethanol⁶ and a stock solution ($\sim 0.2M$) was prepared. Ceric ammonium nitrate solution was prepared in 0.1 *M* sulphuric acid. Acetic acid (G.R.) was redistilled over solid potassium dichromate before use.

Reactant solutions were prepared in the required amount of acid and other reagents as the case may be. Surfactant was always taken in the oxidant flask. Ce^{IV} was found to be stable in presence of NDPC. Both the reactants were thermostated for 45 min to attain equilibrium and the reactions were initiated by mixing 25 ml each at the desired temperature. Progress of the reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots (5 ml) at different time intervals, placed into a known excess of standard ferrous ammonium sulphate and the residual ferrous solution was titrated against standard potassium dichromate solution using *N*-phenylanthranilic acid as the indicator. Results were reproducible within the limits of experimental error.

The cmc value of NDPC was determined in aqueous acetic acid (20%) by conductometrically⁷ in presence of the substrate only. The value was found to be 0.016 *M* which was very close to the reported⁸ value of 0.0151 *M*.

Results and Discussion

Kinetic study of acetophenone oxidation by Ce^{IV} in absence of the micelle: Kinetic results of the oxidation of acetophenone and substituted acetophenones by Ce^{IV} in aqueous systems in absence of the micelles have been reported and mechanistic details have been examined. Active cerium species in presence of sulphuric acid⁹ was reported to be $Ce(OH)^{3+}$ whereas in $HClO_4$ medium¹⁰ it was identified as $Ce(aq)^{4+}$.

Kinetic studies in presence of cationic micelles: Oxidation studies for acetophenone, *p*-methoxyacetophenone and *p*-nitroacetophenone by ceric ammonium nitrate in 20% acetic acid-water medium (v/v) containing sulphuric acid (0.1–1 *M*) were carried out in presence of NDPC. Kinetics indicated first order dependence in both substrate and oxidant, and the order in $[H^+]$ is negative but fractional; an observation also found in aqueous system. The retardation by $[H^+]$ is explained by the hydrolysis of Ce^{4+} species to $Ce(OH)^{3+}$,

Micellar Effect on Oxidation of Acetophenones by Cerium(IV)

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Manuscript received 28 September 1989,
revised 6 December 1990, accepted 24 April 1991

CATALYSIS of electron transfer reactions by micelles has assumed importance as the micelles mimic natural membranes. Most of the electron transfer reactions studied under the influence of micelles involve inorganic moieties¹⁻³ except a few cases⁴. Recently, in a report of micellar catalysis in the oxidation of hydrocarbons⁵ by Ce^{IV} , the mechanism of catalysis was discussed basing on the product

Fig. 1. Plot of k_{obs} vs [NDPC] for acetophenone and substituted acetophenones: (1) p -NO₂-acetophenone, [H⁺]=0.315 M, (2) p -OCH₃-acetophenone, [H⁺]=0.763 M, (3) p -OCH₃-acetophenone, [H⁺]=0.523 M, (4) p -OCH₃-acetophenone, [H⁺]=0.315 M, (5) acetophenone, [H⁺]=0.523 M and (6) acetophenone, [H⁺]=0.315 M; temp.=35°, solvent: AcOH-H₂O (20 : 80%, v/v)

Thus the Ce(OH)³⁺ is considered the effective species in presence of the surfactant.

Oxidation rates in presence of NDPC are not further affected by presence of salts like K₂SO₄, similar to that occurring in absence of surfactants. This ensures that the reactions occur between a charged and a neutral species¹¹. The cationic micelle inhibits the rate. Plot of k_{obs} vs [NDPC] results in continuous decrease and finally levels off (Fig. 1). The observation is similar to that observed by Bunton and Cerichelli² in the oxidation of ferrocene by ferric salts in presence of CTAB. The results can be explained by the pseudo-phase model which leads to the rate equation,

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_w + k_m K_B ([D] - cmc)}{1 + K_B ([D] - cmc)} \quad (2)$$

where, K_B is the binding constant in terms of the concentration of micellised surfactant, k_w and k_m are the first order rate constants in the aqueous and micellar pseudo-phase respectively and include the concentration of Ce⁴⁺ ion in these pseudo-phases and k_{ψ} is the observed rate constant. Equation (2)

can be rearranged to the form equation (2a) to enable easy solution,

$$\frac{1}{k_w - k_{\psi}} = \frac{1}{k_w - k_m} + \frac{1}{(k_w - k_m) K_B ([D] - cmc)} \quad (2a)$$

Validity of equation (2a) was demonstrated by plotting $1/(k_w - k_{\psi})$ vs $1/([D] - cmc)$ which is found to be excellently linear (Fig. 2). From the slope and the intercept of the plot, K_B (binding constant) was computed, and from the intercept, k_m was computed. The values of K_B and k_m for some of the reactions are given in Table 2. Magnitude of the k_m is significantly small indicating that the reaction occurs in the aqueous phase than in the micellar phase. Further, magnitude of K_B indicates depletion of the substrate concentration in the aqueous phase which results in lowering of rate with increasing surfactant concentration.

In addition, there appears to be significant structural influence in the binding constant as seen from the relative magnitudes of K_B values of acetophenone and p -methoxyacetophenone. Greater hydrophobicity of acetophenone over that of the

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/(k_w - k_\psi)$ vs $1/([D] - \text{cmc})$ for acetophenone and substituted acetophenones: (1) *p*-NO₂-acetophenone, $[H^+] = 0.315 M$, (2) *p*-OCH₃-acetophenone, $[H^+] = 0.768 M$, (3) *p*-OCH₃-acetophenone, $[H^+] = 0.315 M$, (4) *p*-OCH₃-acetophenone, $[H^+] = 0.523 M$, (5) acetophenone, $[H^+] = 0.523 M$ and (6) acetophenone, $[H^+] = 0.315 M$; temp = 35°, solvent: AcOH - H₂O (20 : 80%, v/v).

TABLE 1—CORR. COEFF. VALUES IN OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES BY Ce^{IV} AT 35° IN PRESENCE OF NDPC IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID MEDIUM

[Substrate]	[H ⁺] M	Corr. coeff.	No. of points
Acetophenone	0.315	0.922	07
	0.523	0.991	12
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-acetophenone	0.315	0.995	04
	0.523	0.876	03
	0.768	0.985	04
<i>p</i> -Nitro-acetophenone	0.315	0.982	06

p-methoxy derivative is responsible for larger K_B values observed in case of acetophenone. On the other hand, binding of *p*-nitroacetophenone is stronger compared to the *p*-methoxy derivative to the micellar medium presumably because of greater electrostatic attraction between the nitro group and positively charged micellar surface. Thus one can qualitatively conclude that the aromatic group of the moiety is situated on the stern layer with the aliphatic end in the interior of the micelle^{12,13}. Once the substrate moiety is absorbed into the micellar surface, approach of the cerium species which is positively charged is prevented by the counter ion. Hence the reaction is inhibited in presence of the micelles. The model (equation 2) suggested by Menger and Portnoy¹⁴ and successfully

employed by Bunton and Cerichelli³ and many other workers¹⁵ to explain reactions in presence of micelles could be used successfully to explain the present results.

Reactions influenced by surfactants have been viewed as models of enzyme catalysed reactions. A kinetic model similar to Hill model¹⁶ has been used by Piszkiwicz¹⁷ to explain the catalysis of bimolecular reactions by surfactants. Piszkiwicz model relates cooperativity between substrate and the surfactant and its contribution to the rate is given by equation (3)

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_m[D]^n + k_0 K_D}{K_D + [D]^n} \quad (3)$$

where, K_D is the dissociation constant of micellised detergent back to its components, k_m and k_0 are the rate constants in presence and absence of the surfactants and k_ψ is observed rate constant. Rearrangement of the equation results in

$$\log \left(\frac{k_{\text{obs}} - k_0}{k_m - k_{\text{obs}}} \right) = n + \log [D] - \log K_D \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) has the advantage that it does not need the knowledge of critical micellar concentration. This helps a large number of data to come under the purview of calculation.

Although the equation was derived for the micelle catalysed reactions showing a maximum rate¹⁸ followed by inhibition, the model was applied to the present system where the reaction is inhibited by the micelle over the whole range as already mentioned.

For making the equation applicable in the present study, k_m computed from equation (2a) was employed. Using this value of k_m left-hand-side term of equation (4) was calculated. Plots of this term against $\log[D]$ was found to be satisfactorily linear (corr. coeff. values at different acidity are given in Table 1) for the reaction studied. From the slope and intercept n (=cooperativity) and $\log K_D$ values calculated at different acidities are given

TABLE 2—VALUES OF K_B AND k_m IN OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES BY Ce^{IV} AT 35° IN PRESENCE OF NDPC IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID MEDIUM

[Substrate]	[H ⁺] M	K_B	k_m $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Acetophenone	0.315	234.0	1.172
	0.523	349.6	1.103
<i>p</i> -Methoxy-acetophenone	0.315	47.7	1.138
	0.523	61.2	1.468
	0.768	27.3	1.659
<i>p</i> -Nitro-acetophenone	0.315	107.1	6.590

in Table 3. The values of n and $\log K_D$ are comparable with those listed by Piszkiwicz¹⁷. One now examines if there is any trend in these n and K_D values. Apparently, there is increase in the values of both the quantities when the acidity of the medium increases as seen from the data of *p*-methoxyaceto-

TABLE 3—VALUES OF n AND $\log K_D$ IN OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONES BY CeIV AT 35° IN PRESENCE OF NDPC IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID MEDIUM

[Substrate]	[H ⁺] M	n	$-\log K_D$
Acetophenone	0.315	1.156	0.60
	0.523	1.478	1.28
<i>p</i> -Methoxyacetophenone	0.315	1.143	1.60
	0.523	1.344	1.88
	0.768	1.900	2.00
<i>p</i> -Nitroacetophenone	0.315	1.017	1.00

phenone. However, no correlation of either n or K_D is observed with structural parameters like inductive substituent constant (σ).

From analogy with enzymatic reactions, a value of $n > 1$ obtained in micellar catalysed reactions has been termed as positive cooperativity which means stimulation of the interaction of the first molecule with the micelle. A value of $n < 1$ has been termed as negative cooperativity meaning inhibition of interaction of additional molecules of substrate by the interaction of the first molecule with the micelle. Thus the magnitude of n is found to be greater than unity for acetophenones. There seems to be positive cooperativity in the reactions studied. As retardation of the oxidation was observed over the whole range of micellar concentration for all the substrates, the probable reason of retardation may be attributed to the nature of the medium or deactivation of the ionic reactants, namely the cerium species rather than to cooperativity.

The magnitudes of n and $-\log K_D$ were used by Piszkiwicz to find an analogy for micellar-catalysed reactions with the enzyme-catalysed reactions. However these data in the present study do not throw much light into the micellar model proposed by Piszkiwicz.

Acknowledgement

The authors' thanks are due to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial help and the award of fellowship to one of them (B.P.S.).

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